

THE ESSENCE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF METHODS AND METHODS USED IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Mansurova Mokhinur Akmalovna

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7115481>

Abstract: This article analyzes the concept, essence, features and methods of teaching methods used in teaching foreign languages.

Key words: foreign language, methodology, reading, listening, speaking, grammar, theory, language materials.

In the beginning of the 60s of the last century, attempts were made to define the methodology as a set of teaching methods in the methodology of teaching foreign languages. Methods of familiarization with language materials, teaching methods and similar things appeared. In this regard, there was a duality in the understanding of this term. Before considering methodological directions, some clarifications regarding the term "method" should be made. In local methodical literature, this term has two meanings: method as a methodological direction and method as a method - a set of teaching methods. The duality of the meaning of this term is related to the following circumstances. Initially, the first meaning of this term came from methodological literature: natural method, direct method, etc. This term meant a set of special teaching principles, that is, a special educational system characterized by basic instructions. It should be noted that in this sense, the method is distinguished by a complex of principles, because individual principles may coincide in different methodological systems.

The review of stylistic directions begins with the oldest method - grammatical translation, which has existed for two centuries and has not been used since the beginning of the twentieth century. Representatives of this tendency believed that learning a foreign language in secondary educational institutions has a general educational value related not only to the gymnastics of the mind and the development of logical thinking achieved as a result of the systematic study of grammar. The formation of thinking based on the study of grammar originated from the Latin language, and studying its grammar was considered the best means of developing logical thinking.

The main principles of teaching this method were as follows:

① The course is based on a grammatical system, which has determined the choice of material, including the choice of vocabulary, and the overall construction of the course. This position was justified by the fact that learning grammar allows for the development of thinking, a general educational problem.

② The main material for teaching was the texts that reflected the original language for written speech according to the teachers of that time.

☒ The dictionary was considered only as an illustrative material for learning grammar. Since it is believed that the words of different languages differ from each other only in sound and graphics, and not in meaning, compatibility and difference, it is recommended to memorize them out of context as a separate unit.

☒ Analysis and synthesis were recognized as leading processes of logical thinking. In this regard, much attention was paid to analyzing the text from the point of view of grammar, memorizing the rules, and building foreign language sentences on this basis. Sometimes this method is called analytical-synthetic.

☒ The main means of semanticizing linguistic material was translation (from a foreign language into a native language and from a native language into a foreign language).

Let's take a look at the learning process using this method. As mentioned above, the training is based on selected texts to reflect the grammatical material being studied. Analysis and translation of the text took an important place in the educational process. Some Methodists, such as G. Ollendorf, believed that the content of translations should be funny and disgusting for students, so they should pay attention to the grammatical side of the sentences. It is not difficult to understand that with such a "method" it is impossible to know even elementary languages.

At the end of the 18th century, another type of translation method appeared - the text translation method. Representatives of this trend also believed that the main goal of education is general education. However, they understood it as the general intellectual development of students based on the study of original works of art. The main rules of this method are reduced to the following principles:

☒ Education is based on the original foreign text, which includes all the linguistic phenomena necessary for understanding any text.

☒ Assimilation of linguistic material is carried out as a result of text analysis, mechanical memorization and translation, as a rule, verbatim.

☒ The main learning process is related to analysis - the main method of logical thinking. It follows from these rules that the text is the center of all work in language, a position that has existed in methodology for a long time.

It should be noted that, despite certain shortcomings, a number of techniques developed by the text-translation method entered the arsenal of subsequent methodological trends. Thus, working on the text served as a basis for the

formation of such types as reading (or explanatory) reading. The technique includes the practice of reverse translation.

Both methods considered above have common aspects and are related to translation, because translation is the main means of semanticization and assimilation of linguistic material. Both methods are characterized by separating form from content. So, in the grammar-translation method, all attention is focused on grammar, and the content and vocabulary of the texts are not taken into account. In the method of textual translation, all attention is focused on the content and features of the texts, grammar is studied out of order, and rules are given from time to time.

The main principles of teaching according to the method of M. Berlitz were as follows:

1. The purpose of the training is to develop oral speech.
2. Learning the material should be based on imitation and similarities. Therefore, the comparison with native language and rules is redundant.
3. Unraveling the meaning of words, grammar should be done with the help of Visualization (objects, actions, pictures).
4. The main form of work is dialogue.
5. All materials of the language are first received by ear (acquiring pronunciation), then it is developed orally (with different authors in different ways in terms of duration), and after a long time, from individual words is read from.

All exercises are built according to these principles. Thus, in M. Berlitz's textbook, the first pages of the book are mainly filled with pictures drawn with plates depicting individual objects for the school audience. This oral opening, involving the introduction of new material in the following paragraphs, was justified by the author on the grounds that the student should first hear the original pronunciation and the pattern to be imitated. Vocabulary semanticization was carried out with the help of visualization, facial expressions played an important role. In cases where the indicated tools could not help, the teacher switched to semanticization with the help of the context. Question-and-answer exercises were widely used as exercises. Learning to read is built in an interesting way. At first, previously learned words were read without dividing them into parts, and only after several lessons was explained the reading of individual letters and phrases. In other words, learning how to read words, questions, and answers happened as if from the "voice" of the teacher. Thus, the main attention was paid to dialogic speech. The vitality of the schools of M.

Berlitz lies in the fact that the ability to conduct dialogue was achieved on the basis of a small material, that is, it was demanded in connection with the struggle for commodity markets.

Unlike M. Berlitz, F. Guen was a teacher and, by his own admission, used different methods. In general, he concluded that it was ineffective. Once, while observing the children, they found that the children, while learning their native language, accompanied their actions with toys in chronological order with comments: "The bear is lying down. The bear falls asleep. The bear sleeps well" and similar things. Therefore, the main place in F. Gouin's system is occupied by the position that it is natural to teach language in a chronological sequence based on human actions, emotions. This led to the second position of his system - around a sentence that combines both grammar and vocabulary. F. Guen first began to distinguish the concepts of three groups of phrases: objective, subjective and figurative. According to these groups, lines are built based on the breakdown of action. Let's explain this with a concrete example of "writing a letter": I take the paper. I take out the pen. I remove the cap from the inkwell. I dip my pen into the inkwell and so on, he proposed a series of up to 75 sequences in a sentence-based tutorial. The workflow for such a sequence went as follows.

First, the teacher performs actions and comments on them at the same time. Then the students repeat each sentence after the teacher. After that, the teacher says separate phrases, students perform actions. Then the strong student says the sentences and the others do the actions. Oral work ends with the naming of actions (by all students) and their implementation. After this practice, students write in a notebook one after the other. After such training on the basis of semi-mechanical imitation, students mainly mastered oral speech using limited materials. Otherwise, F. Huyen followed the same methodological principles as M. Berlitz. M. Walter was a well-known representative of the natural method. He, like F. Gouin, connected the teaching of a foreign language with the active activities of students and attached great importance to the emotional side of perception of the surrounding world. Accordingly, he tried to bring the teaching closer to introducing students to the language to be translated. Thus, teaching German in Scotland, he furnished his auditorium in the form of a German beer hall. If at the initial stage the acquisition of language material was based on actions and their explanations, then at the advanced stages students acted out scenes, described some characters. Thus, M. Voltaire went a little further than F. Guen in the connection between imitation and imitation of activities and

movements. His stylistic technique is interesting - a recommendation for working with painting. Thus, in his opinion, when describing a picture, one should pay attention to the parts of the object, their characteristics (size, shape, color), actions with this object, and finally, its application. It should be noted that M. Voltaire was the first to organize exercises into groups as a means of memorizing words. So, he proposed to group words according to the principle of synonyms and antonyms, according to the thematic principle according to similar words. After a brief examination of the foundations of the natural method, it should be noted that although it does not have a sufficient scientific basis and its authors were ordinary teachers, it is a very significant contribution to the methodology of what remains there to this day. added

First of all, it should be noted that representatives of the natural method proposed a system of continuous semanticization of vocabulary:

- 1) showing the object, its image, demonstrating movement using facial expressions;
- 2) reveal the meaning of words using synonyms, antonyms or definitions;
- 3) to reveal the meaning with the help of context.

All these methods of semanticization have survived many methodological directions and entered our methodology. Of course, the modern methodology uses different types of grouping proposed by M. Voltaire as one of the possible methods of systematizing the dictionary, first of all, on the thematic basis. It has found its place in modern styles and interpretation of actions, especially in the initial stage, as well as in the performance of scenes. All this allows us to confirm that the heritage of the natural method has not been lost.

Methodological principles of teaching the direct method were as follows:

☒ The basis of teaching is oral speech, because any language is inherently sound, and the leading place is occupied by sound and kinesthetic sensations (sensations of the speech apparatus), which have been proven by psychology.

☒ Exclusion of native language and translation. This position was based on the research that the words of the native language do not correspond to the words of the studied meaning, express different concepts and so on, because each nation has its own worldview, the system of concepts reflected in the language there is.

☒ Special importance was given to phonetics and pronunciation, because mastering the sound side of speech is an indispensable condition for oral speech. This conclusion was made based on the study of the sound side of the language. As a result, pronunciation methods were developed.

☒ Based on the position of Gestalt psychology, it is not the sum of its components and the linguistic position of words in the polysemy, representatives of the direct method recommended studying words only in context.

☒ It was proposed to learn grammar based on induction in this method. Based on a well-studied text, students made observations on the text and extracted rules. Espersen O. called it "observational grammar". Later, these rules were introduced into the system.

References:

1. Conversations about a foreign language lesson: a guide for students of pedagogical institutes / Passov E.I., Kolova T.I., Volkova T.A., Dobronravova T.N., Voronova O.M., Krainova E.A. - L., "Education", - 1975.
2. Bim I.L. On the issue of the methodology of teaching foreign languages. // IYaSh.-1974.- No. 2.-S.19-32.
3. Volovin A.V. Communicative approach to foreign language learning in British and American methodological systems // Communicative approach to foreign language learning: a collection of articles. scientific. works, volume 275 - M., 1985.
4. Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova "Use of innovative technologies in the educational process" Science and Education Issue 3, March 2022;
5. Introduction to the communicative methodology of teaching English: a guide for Russian teachers - Oxford University Press, 1997.

